

A_1 and A_3 , A_3 lies between A_2 and A_4 , etc. and the segments AA_1 , A_1A_2 , A_2A_3 , A_3A_4 , ... are congruent to one another.

Then, among this series of points, not always there exists a certain point A_n such that B lies between A and A_n .

For example:

let A be a point in δ_1 - f_1 , and B a point on f_1 , B different from P ;

on the line AB consider the points A_1 , A_2 , A_3 , A_4 , ... in between A and B , such that AA_1 , A_1A_2 , A_2A_3 , A_3A_4 , etc. are congruent to one another;

then we find that there is no point behind B (considering the direction from A to B), because B is a limit point (the line AB ends in B).

The Bolzano's (intermediate value) theorem may not hold in the Critical Zone of the Model.

Can you readers find a better model for this anti-geometry?

References:

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On certain new inequalities and limits for the Smarandache function

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I. Inequalities

1) If $n \geq 4$ is an even number, then $S(n) \leq \frac{n}{2}$.

—Indeed, $\frac{n}{2}$ is integer, $\frac{n}{2} > 2$, so in $(\frac{n}{2})! = 1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdots \frac{n}{2}$ we can simplify with 2, so $n \mid (\frac{n}{2})!$.

This implies clearly that $S(n) \leq \frac{n}{2}$.

2) If $n > 4$ is an even number, then $S(n^2) \leq n$

—By $n! = 1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdots \frac{n}{2} \cdots n$, since we can simplify with 2, for $n > 4$ we get that $n^2 \mid n!$. This clearly implies the above stated inequality. For factorials, the above inequality can be much improved, namely one has:

3) $S((m!)^2) \leq 2m$ and more generally, $S((m!)^n) \leq n \cdot m$ for all positive integers m and n .

—First remark that $\frac{(mn)!}{(m!)^n} = \frac{(mn)!}{m!(mn-m)!} \cdot \frac{(mn-m)!}{m!(mn-2m)!} \cdots \frac{(2m)!}{m! \cdot m!} =$

$= C_{2m}^m \cdot C_{3m}^m \cdots C_{nm}^m$, where $C_n^k = \binom{n}{k}$ denotes a binomial coefficient. Thus $(m!)^n$ divides $(mn)!$, implying the stated inequality. For $n = 2$ one obtains the first part.

4) Let $n > 1$. Then $S((n!)^{(n-1)!}) \leq n!$

—We will use the well-known result that the product of n consecutive integers is divisible by $n!$. By $(n!)! = 1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdots n \cdot ((n+1)(n+2) \cdots 2n) \cdots ((n-1)!-1) \cdots (n-1)! \cdot n$ each group is divisible by $n!$, and there are $(n-1)!$ groups, so $(n!)^{(n-1)!}$ divides $(n!)!$. This gives the stated inequality.

5) For all m and n one has $[S(m), S(n)] \leq S(m \cdot S(n)) \leq [m, n]$, where $[a, b]$ denotes the

$\ell \cdot c \cdot m$ of a and b .

–If $m = \prod_{p_i} a_i$, $n = \prod q_j^{b_j}$ are the canonical representations of m , resp. n , then it is well-known that $S(m) = S(a_i)$ and $S(n) = S(q_j^{b_j})$, where $S(a_i) = \max \{S(a_i) : i = 1, \dots, r\}$; $S(q_j^{b_j}) = \max \{S(q_j^{b_j}) : j = 1, \dots, h\}$, with r and h the number of prime divisors of m , resp. n . Then clearly $[S(m), S(n)] \leq S(m) \cdot S(n) \leq \prod_{p_i} a_i \cdot \prod q_j^{b_j} \leq [m, n]$

$$6) \quad \underline{S(m), S(n)} \geq \frac{S(m) \cdot S(n)}{m n} \cdot (m, n) \text{ for all } m \text{ and } n$$

$$\text{–Since } (S(m), S(n)) = \frac{S(m) \cdot S(n)}{[S(m), S(n)]} \geq \frac{S(m) \cdot S(n)}{[m, n]} = \frac{S(m) \cdot S(n)}{n m} \cdot (m, n)$$

by 5) and the known formula $[m, n] = \frac{m n}{(m, n)}$.

$$7) \quad \frac{(S(m), S(n))}{(m, n)} \geq \left(\frac{S(m n)}{m n} \right)^2 \text{ for all } m \text{ and } n$$

–Since $S(m n) \leq m S(n)$ and $S(m n) \leq n S(m)$ (See [1]), we have $\left(\frac{S(m n)}{m n} \right)^2 \leq \frac{S(m) S(n)}{m n}$,

and the result follows by 6).

$$8) \quad \text{We have } \left(\frac{S(m n)}{m n} \right)^2 \leq \frac{S(m) S(n)}{m n} \leq \frac{1}{(m n)}$$

–This follows by 7) and the stronger inequality from 6), namely $S(m) S(n) \leq [m n] = \frac{m n}{(m, n)}$

Corollary $S(m n) \leq \frac{m n}{\sqrt{m n}}$

$$9) \quad \text{Max } \{S(m), S(n)\} \geq \frac{S(m n)}{(m n)} \text{ for all } m, n; \text{ where } (m, n) \text{ denotes the } g \cdot c \cdot d \text{ of } m \text{ and } n.$$

–We apply the known result: $\max \{S(m), S(n)\} = S([m, n])$ On the other hand, since

$$[m, n] \mid m \cdot n, \text{ by Corollary 1 from our paper [1] we get } \frac{S(m n)}{m n} \leq \frac{S([m, n])}{[m, n]}.$$

$$\text{Since } [m, n] = \frac{m n}{(m, n)},$$

The result follows:

Remark. Inequality g) compliments Theorem 3 from [1],

namely that $\max \{S(m), S(n)\} \leq S(m n)$.

10) Let $d(n)$ be the number of divisors of n . Then $\frac{S(n!)}{n!} \leq \frac{S(n^{d(n)/2})}{n^{d(n)/2}}$

—We will use the known relation $\prod_{k|n} k = n^{d(n)/2}$, where the product is extended over all divisors k of n . Since this product divides $\prod_{k \leq n} k = n!$, by Corollary 1 from [1] we can write

$$\frac{S(n!)}{n!} \leq \frac{S(\prod_{k|n} k)}{\prod_{k|n} k}, \text{ which gives the desired result.}$$

Remark If n is of the form m^2 , then $d(n)$ is odd, but otherwise $d(n)$ is even. So, in each case $n^{d(n)/2}$ is a positive integer.

11) For infinitely many n we have $S(n+1) < S(n)$, but for infinitely many m one has

$$S(m+1) > S(m).$$

—This is a simple application of 1). Indeed, let $n = p - 1$, where $p \geq 5$ is a prime. Then, by

1) we have $S(n) = S(p - 1) \leq \frac{p-1}{2} < p$. Since $p = S(p)$, we have $S(p - 1) < S(p)$.

Let in the same manner $n = p + 1$. Then, as above, $S(p + 1) \leq \frac{p+1}{2} < p = S(p)$.

12) Let p be a prime. Then $S(p! + 1) > S(p!)$ and $S(p! - 1) > S(p!)$

—Clearly, $S(p!) = p$. Let $p! + 1 = \prod q_j^{\partial_j}$ be the prime factorization of $p! + 1$. Here each $q_j > p$, thus $S(p! + 1) = S(q_j^{\partial_j})$ (for certain j) $\geq S(p^{\partial_j}) \geq S(p) = p$. The same proof applies to the case $p! - 1$.

Remark: This offers a new proof for M).

13) Let P_k be the k th prime number. Then $S(p_1 p_2 \dots P_k + 1) > S(p_1 p_2 \dots P_k)$ and

$$S(p_1 p_2 \dots P_k - 1) > S(p_1 p_2 \dots P_k)$$

—Almost the same proof as in 12) is valid, by remarking that $S(p_1 p_2 \dots P_k) = P_k$ (since

$$p_1 < p_2 < \dots < p_k).$$

14) For infinitely many n one has $(S(n)^2) < S(n-1) \cdot S(n+1)$ and for infinitely many m ,

$$(S(m))^2 > S(m-1) \cdot S(m+1).$$

—By $S(p+1) < p$ and $S(p-1) < p$ (See the proof in 11) we have

$$\frac{S(p+1)}{S(p)} < \frac{S(p)}{S(p)} < \frac{S(p)}{S(p-1)}. \text{ Thus } (S(p))^2 > S(p-1) \cdot S(p+1).$$

On the other hand, by putting $x_n = \frac{S(n+1)}{S(n)}$, we shall see in part II,

that $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = +\infty$. Thus $x_{n-1} < x_n$ for infinitely many n , giving

$$(S(n))^2 < S(n-1) \cdot S(n+1).$$

II. Limits:

$$1) \quad \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(n)}{n} = 0 \text{ and } \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(n)}{n} = 1$$

—Clearly, $\frac{S(n)}{n} > 0$. Let $n = 2^m$. Then, since $S(2^m) \leq 2m$, and $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{2m}{2^m} = 0$, we have

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(2^m)}{2^m} = 0, \text{ proving the first part. On the other hand, it is well known that } \frac{S(n)}{n} \leq 1.$$

For $n = p_k$ (the k th prime), one has $\frac{S(p_k)}{p_k} = 1 \rightarrow 1$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$, proving the second part.

Remark: With the same proof, we can derive that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(n^r)}{n} = 0$ for all integers r .

—As above $S(2^{kr}) \leq 2kr$, and $\frac{2kr}{2^k} \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ (r fixed), which gives the result.

$$2) \quad \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(n+1)}{S(n)} = 0 \text{ and } \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(n+1)}{S(n)} = +\infty$$

—Let p_r denote the r th prime. Since $(p_{\Lambda} \dots p_r, 1) = 1$, Dirichlet's theorem on arithmetical progressions assures the existence of a prime p of the form $p = a \cdot p_{\Lambda} \dots p_r - 1$.

Then $S(p+1) = S(ap_{\Lambda} \dots p_r) \leq a \cdot S(p_{\Lambda} \dots p_r)$ by $S(mn) \leq mS(n)$ (see [1])

But $S(p_{\Lambda} \dots p_r) = \max \{p_{\Lambda}, \dots, p_r\} = p_r$. Thus $\frac{S(p+1)}{S(p)} \leq \frac{ap_r}{ap_{\Lambda} \dots p_r - 1} \leq$

$\frac{p_r}{p_{\Lambda} \dots p_r - 1} \rightarrow 0$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$. This gives the first part.

Let now p be a prime of the form $p = bp_{\Lambda} \dots p_r + 1$.

Then $S(p-1) = S(bp_1 \cdots p_r) \leq b S(p_1 \cdots p_r) = b \cdot p_r$,

and $\frac{S(p-1)}{S(p)} \leq \frac{bp_r}{bp_1 \cdots p_{r+1}} \leq \frac{p_r}{p_1 \cdots p_r} \rightarrow 0$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$.

3) $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} [S(n+1) - S(n)] = -\infty$ and $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} [S(n+1) - S(n)] = +\infty$

—We have $S(p+1) - S(p) \leq \frac{p+1}{2} - p = \frac{-p+1}{2} \rightarrow -\infty$ for an odd prime

p (see 1) and 11)). On the other hand, $S(p) - S(p-1) \geq p - \frac{p-1}{2} = \frac{p+1}{2} \rightarrow \infty$

(Here $S(p) = p$), where $p-1$ is odd for $p \geq 5$. This finishes the proof.

4) Let $\sigma(n)$ denotes the sum of divisors of n . Then $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(\sigma(n))}{n} = 0$

—This follows by the argument of 2) for $n = p$. Then $\sigma(p) = p+1$ and $\frac{S(p+1)}{p} \rightarrow 0$, where

$\{p\}$ is the sequence constructed there.

5) Let $\varphi(n)$ be the Euler totient function. Then $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(\varphi(n))}{n} = 0$

—Let the set of primes $\{p\}$ be defined as in 2). Since $\varphi(p) = p-1$ and $\frac{S(p-1)}{p} = \frac{S(p-1)}{S(p)} \rightarrow 0$,

the assertion is proved. The same result could be obtained by taking $n = 2^k$. Then, since

$\varphi(2^k) = 2^{k-1}$, and $\frac{S(2^{k-1})}{2^k} \leq \frac{2 \cdot (k-1)}{2^k} \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$, the assertion follows:

6) $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(S(n))}{n} = 0$ and $\max_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \frac{S(S(n))}{n} = 1$.

—Let $n = p!$ (p prime). Then, since $S(p!) = p$ and $S(p) = p$, from $\frac{p}{p!} \rightarrow 0$ ($p \rightarrow \infty$)

we get the first result. Now, clearly $\frac{S(S(n))}{n} \leq \frac{S(n)}{n} \leq 1$. By letting $n = p$ (prime), clearly

one has $\frac{S(S(p))}{p} = 1$, which shows the second relation.

7) $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sigma(S(n))}{S(n)} = 1$.

—Clearly, $\frac{\sigma(k)}{k} > 1$. On the other hand, for $n = p$ (prime), $\frac{\sigma(S(p))}{S(p)} = \frac{p+1}{p} \rightarrow 1$ as $p \rightarrow \infty$.

8) Let $Q(n)$ denote the greatest prime power divisor of n . Then $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\varphi(S(n))}{\partial(n)} = 0$.

—Let $n = p_1^k \cdots p_r^k$ ($k > 1$, fixed). Then, clearly $\partial(n) = p_r^k$.

By $S(n) = S(p_r^k)$ (since $S(p_i^k) > S(p_i^k)$ for $i < k$) and $S(p_r^k) = j \cdot p_r$, with $j \leq k$ (which is

known) and by $\varphi(j p_k) \leq j \cdot \varphi(p_r) \leq k(p_r - 1)$, we get $\frac{\varphi(S(n))}{\partial(n)} \leq \frac{k \cdot (p_r - 1)}{p_r^k} \rightarrow 0$ as

$r \rightarrow \infty$ (k fixed).

$$9) \quad \lim_{\substack{m \rightarrow \infty \\ m \text{ even}}} \frac{S(m^2)}{m^2} = 0$$

—By 2) we have $\frac{S(m^2)}{m^2} \leq \frac{1}{m}$ for $m > 4$, even. This clearly implies the above remark.

Remark. It is known that $\frac{S(m)}{m} \leq \frac{2}{3}$ if $m \neq 4$ is composite. From $\frac{S(m^2)}{m^2} \leq \frac{1}{m} < \frac{2}{3}$ for $m > 4$,

for the composite numbers of the perfect squares we have a very strong improvement.

$$10) \quad \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sigma(S(n))}{n} = 0$$

—By $\sigma(n) = \sum_{d|n} d = n \sum_{d|n} \frac{1}{d} \leq n \sum_{d=1}^n \frac{1}{d} < n \cdot (2 \log n)$, we get $\sigma(n) < 2n \log n$ for $n > 1$. Thus

$$\frac{\sigma(S(n))}{n} < \frac{2 S(n) \log S(n)}{n}. \text{ For } n = 2^k \text{ we have } S(2^k) \leq 2k, \text{ and since } \frac{4k \log 2k}{2^k} \rightarrow 0$$

($k \rightarrow \infty$), the result follows.

$$11) \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sqrt[3]{S(n)} = 1$$

—This simple relation follows by $1 \leq S(n) \leq n$, so $1 \leq \sqrt[3]{S(n)} \leq \sqrt[3]{n}$; and by $\sqrt[3]{n} \rightarrow 1$

as $n \rightarrow \infty$. However, 11) is one of a (few) limits, which exists for the Smarandache function.

Finally, we shall prove that:

$$12) \quad \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sigma(n S(n))}{n S(n)} = +\infty.$$

—We will use the facts that $S(p!) = p$, $\frac{\sigma(p!)}{p!} = \prod_{d|p!} \frac{1}{d} \geq 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \dots + \frac{1}{p} \rightarrow \infty$ as $p \rightarrow \infty$, and the inequality $\sigma(ab) \geq a\sigma(b)$ (see [2]).

Thus $\frac{\sigma(S(p!)p!)}{p! \cdot S(p!)} \geq \frac{S(p!) \cdot \sigma(p!)}{p! \cdot p} = \frac{\sigma(p!)}{p!} \rightarrow \infty$. Thus, for the sequence $\{n\} = \{p!\}$, the results follows.

References

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